

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Deliverable D2.5

Rapid Response Report

WP 2 – T2.1

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Contributing Participants	ANSES, T2.1 partners
Responsible author(s)	Maria Tannous / Anses / maria.tannous@anses.fr
Co-authors	T2.1 co-leaders : Christophe Rousselle / Anses / Christophe.rousselle@anses.fr Georges Kass / EFSA / Georges.KASS@efsa.europa.eu Wim De Coen / ECHA / Wim.DECOEN@echa.europa.eu Safia Korati / ECHA / Safia.korati@echa.europa.eu
Reviewers internal to WP	Maria Uhl/ EAA / maria.uhl@umweltbundesamt.at / WP2 co-leader Magnus Lofstedt / EEA / Magnus.Lofstedt@eea.europa.eu / WP2 co-leader
Reviewers external to WP	Peter Droell / DG RTD / Peter.Droell@ec.europa.eu / GB vice-chair Thomas Jakl / BMK / thomas.jakl@bmk.gv.at / GB chair Cornelia Marschel / BMUV / cornelia.marschel@bmuv.bund.de / GB vice-chair
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¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other program participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

Version	Date	Reviewer name/Institutions	Short description of changes
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Version 2	11/10/2023	Task 2.1 partners	Minor vocabulary suggestions Reducing the time to respond Inclusion of a new case study
Version 3	22/12/2023	HaDEA	Minor revision
Version 4	09/02/2024	Authors	Minor modifications Addition of the response document of the first urgent request

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Abstract

A Rapid Response Mechanism has been put in place to manage the possibility of incorporating new urgent requests in PARC's work program, either by creating a new project or task or, by integrating it into an existing project. When a submitted urgent request is considered receivable, it will undergo a feasibility assessment by a group of experts within the relevant field. This evaluation will subsequently outline how PARC could integrate this request and formulate a plan accordingly or elucidate the reasons for PARC's inability to tackle this request due to scope issue or feasibility constraints.

Key Words

Rapid Response Mechanism, RRM, urgent needs, emerging compounds, prioritisation

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Acronyms

ANSES: French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety

AWP: Annual Work Plan

CP: Contact Point

CT: ANSES PARC Coordination Team

EC: European Commission

ECHA: European Chemicals Agency

EEA: European Environment Agency

EFSA: European Food Safety Authority

GB: Governing Board

HBM4EU: Human Biomonitoring for EU

MB: Management Board

NHCP: National Hub Contact Point

NH: National Hub

OO: Operational Objective

POC: Proof-of-concept

RRM: Rapid Response Mechanism

SCHEER: Scientific Committee on Health, Environment and Emerging Risks

SF: Stakeholder Forum

UPFAS: Universal PFAS restriction dossier

WP: Work Package

1. Introduction

Over the course of the partnership, Task 2.1 “Priority Setting” is responsible of running three prioritisation rounds in order to determine PARC’s list of priorities. These rounds occur prior to the initiation, midway through and at the end of the partnership. Based on the priorities defined, partners can submit project proposals every year (by September at the latest) to be included in the following Annual Work Plan (AWP). These project suggestions are then discussed within Task 2.1 partners, specific reviewers and Management Board (MB) members to decide on their eventual inclusion in the AWP.

However, if urgent priorities arise, like new urgent needs for information in the EU policy community and at national level, they can still be included in PARC’s priority list through the Rapid Response Mechanism (RRM) developed in this deliverable. In the event of a positive response, it will then be possible to tackle this new priority by initiating a project or a new activity to address it or by integrating it into an existing project. This RRM can also enable certain entities that are not part of the consortium bodies (e.g. Governing board, EU Hub) to express new concerns or urgent projects that PARC should address.

This new project or new activity may require the launch of new surveys on particular chemicals or in particular geographical regions (respecting the scope of countries included in PARC consortium). It can also require the development of new research activities or new approaches to analyse existing data.

2. Methods

PARC’s Rapid Response Mechanism (RRM) is in part inspired by the one from HBM4EU¹ as well as their response document regarding Copper compounds², modified upon comments from Task 2.1 partners to best fit the functioning of PARC and its scope, considering a short and easy-to-fill “Request template for urgent needs”. This mechanism was developed following discussions and meetings with Task 2.1 partners and was subsequently presented to the MB. It underwent a review process by the co-leaders of Task 2.1, WP2 co-leaders and the Governing Body (GB) chairs.

3. Conceptual Rapid Response Mechanism

The main objective of the RRM is to tackle the urgent needs that should be included and prioritised in PARC, given the environmental or human health concerns associated with the request. The RRM is in line with the policy and social impacts of PARC by making it possible to address (newly identified and urgent) Research & Innovation needs in the Chemical Risk Assessment field and by increasing the stakeholders’ involvement in the environment and the health issues. Practically, this transparent mechanism contributes to several Operational Objectives (OO) of PARC:

- OO2 Expand a long-term sustainable network of National Hubs that interact with stakeholders to exchange and feed expertise, knowledge and needs into the Partnership and promote uptake of results.

¹ HBM4EU’s deliverable link “Templates for the submission of urgent requests for new information, one for EU policy makers and one for national policy makers”: <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/work-packages/deliverable-4-1-template-for-the-submission-of-rapid-requests-may-2017/>

² Response document following DG SANTE’s request regarding information needed on Copper compounds. https://www.hbm4eu.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/HBM4EU_4.3_Rapid-respose-Mechanism_Response-Document_Copper-compounds.pdf

- OO3: Define common research and innovation strategies with transparent criteria and prioritisation process to address the regulatory knowledge needs for chemical risk assessment and management.
- OO4: Actively foster the regulatory uptake of knowledge produced under the Partnership in chemical risk assessment and regulatory processes.

In fact, an urgent need is a situation or problem that requires immediate attention and action; policymakers and stakeholders play a crucial role in identifying urgent needs.

The following section details the functioning of the Rapid Response mechanism within PARC, covering the foreseen process all the way from the application, to the analysis of the request, right through to the eventual final response.

3.1. Submitting a new urgent request

3.1.1. Who can submit a request

Authorized request applicants include:

- Governing Board (GB) members³

A GB member willing to activate the RRM will have to notify the GB either during a GB meeting or through a written procedure to the GB co-chairs.

National Hubs Contact Points (NHCPs)⁴ have also the option to activate the RRM through their respective country's GB member. Subsequently, the GB member is responsible for formally submitting the request.

Similarly, an EU Hub CP⁴ must channel their request through their GB member, the EC representative, to initiate a new request.

- Stakeholder Forum (SF)⁵ members

SF members must forward their request to the SF co-chairs, who will then officially submit it to the Task 2.1 co-leaders. The SF co-chairs are well-versed in PARC and its scope, allowing them to filter requests based on their alignment with the RRM. If any uncertainty arises, they must proceed with the submission of the request nonetheless.

³ The Governing Board (GB) is the overarching body of PARC that provides the highest level strategic steering of the Partnership through continuous dialogue by its members at national and international level with the implementation bodies to align PARC activities with activities undertaken at the EU and national levels. The relevant Ministries from all participating countries as well as the relevant Directorates-General of the EC (RTD, GROW, ENV, SANTE, JRC) are part of the GB.

⁴ The Partnership benefits from the organisation of a National Hub (NH) in each participating country with designated National Hub Contact Points (NHCPs) who coordinate the exchange with the national ministries, the national partners (including GS and AEs) and other relevant national stakeholders and contribute to the development of synergies with related national/EU initiatives. Similarly, an EU hub is set-up so the work progress is followed by other interested EU organisations (e.g. EU-OSHA, EMA). ECHA, EFSA and EEA are part of the EU hub.

⁵ The Stakeholder Forum (SF) provides the opportunity for stakeholders to share their vision on how to improve chemical RA in Europe, collect recommendations and develop synergies at the EU and international levels.

3.1.2. How to submit a request

A 'Request Template for urgent needs' will be available on PARC's SharePoint and can be downloaded. The applicant should fill in the template (see below) and share it with Task 2.1 co-leaders via the generic address parc@anses.fr.

The "Request Template for urgent needs" is divided in two sections: **1) Applicant identification, 2) Request formulation, Environmental & Human health concerns**. It is designed to best define the request and understand the nature of the urgent need. The applicants are asked to complete all sections and answer as many questions as possible to enable assessment of proposal.

Request Template for urgent needs

Boxes have been pre-filled in grey and serve as a guide to enhance comprehension of the question's objective. Please feel free to input your responses.

Section 1: Applicant Identification

Applicants should provide contact details in order to identify themselves and allow further communication with them.

➤ Applicant identification	
Applicant	Last name
	First name
	Professional email address
Institution	Institution's name
	Orientation: <i>human health risk or environmental risk</i>
	Involvement in PARC: <i>NHCPs, EU Hub, GB, SF</i>
Country	
Date of completion	

*It is possible to replicate the same table in order to input the information for every associated applicant involved in the request.

Section 2: Request formulation, Environmental & Human health concerns

The applicant is requested to provide background explanation and justification in order to reflect the public's concern regarding the request, the impact of the results and the regulatory / policy relevance. It is crucial to provide a clear explanation of the need and define it with utmost clarity.

Urgent requests may deal with lack of specific information or knowledge needs or urgent new issues on which PARC could deliver action and help. It could involve a short term policy or regulatory need at EU and / or national level. Most importantly, requests must relate to a Human health and/or an environmental concern within the scope of PARC, i.e. assessing the risks posed by chemicals on humans or for the environment, and which must be addressed urgently as it cannot await for the next round of prioritisation.

➤ Request formulation, Environmental & Human health concerns	
Problem formulation and policy context	Describe the relevant background of the need. What are the specific problems that policy-makers or stakeholders wish to address through the research? What major societal issues have prompted you to request research support now?
Public concern	What is the health risk on the human sub-population (to be specified if workers, children, users, etc.) or on the ecosystem?
Research question	What is the research question? Define the request with utmost clarity.
Objectives	Describe the purpose, specific aims, or objectives of PARC's contribution.
Regulations	The Impact of the data requested and what Policy / Regulatory framework does it support: <i>Regulation reference (+which process if possible)</i> <i>e.g.: REACH Restriction, classification, development of methods for endpoints for the Information Requirement, Biocidal Products Regulation (BPR), surface and drinking water ...)</i>
Timeframe to deliver the results	Delivery time for results to remain valid or useful (taking into account the urgency of the request and the policy agenda)

Inclusion in the RRM	Why wasn't the request part of the basic prioritisation process?
Proposed approach for the request's handling	If you already have an idea about how PARC could address the request, kindly document it.
Initiatives outside PARC addressing this need	List the initiatives outside PARC addressing this need (if any) and / or explain why PARC should handle it.
<i>Open text for comments or addition relevant information</i>	

3.2. Assessing the request

3.2.1. Evaluating the eligibility and feasibility of the request

Once the template has been filled-in, the applicant should send it to the Task 2.1 co-leaders using the generic address parc@anses.fr.

The first step of the request assessment involves notifying the GB, MB and SF members. Task 2.1 co-leaders together with the GB will judge the eligibility of the request. If the request is not eligible, it will be withdrawn, with an explanation of the reason provided, and no further evaluation will be conducted. This primary step must be completed within 10 days of receipt of the application.

A request is considered eligible if it addresses the following criteria

- Covering PARC's scope of research: e.g. a substance, an (eco) toxicological endpoint or a method related to human or environmental health. Physical agents are not covered by the scope of PARC for example.
- Addressing a Health concern (causes significant risk in humans or in the ecosystem);
- Addressing a Regulatory challenge e.g. a specific regulatory process such as a REACH restriction requesting biomonitoring data;
- Cannot await a future prioritisation round (grows rapidly or may grow rapidly in scale, urgent for the policy agenda);
- Excluding an emergency situation (mandate being assigned to SCHEER);
- No other initiative is more appropriate to meet this need.

It is essential to point out that the RRM will not cover risk assessment in a context of emergency situation, the mandate being assigned to the Scientific Committee on Health, Environment and Emerging Risks (SCHEER) in the event of a cross-border incident⁶.

If the request is eligible, Task 2.1 partners will launch an internal call for experts in the field. Subsequently, a working group will be set up to assess the new request and eventually its inclusion in the next work program.

The aim of the working group is to gain a better understanding of the research question and to evaluate the feasibility of the research project within PARC. To this end, a meeting will be organised between this working group and the applicants to discuss and understand the nature of the need. Task 2.1 will be in charge of setting up these meetings and following up the request. Based on the discussions, a response document will be drafted by the working group and, if feasible, specifying how the request will be handled,

⁶Guidance on ad hoc rapid risk assessment of serious cross-border chemical health threats performed by the SCHEER: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/2112569b-32fb-11e8-b5fe-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

under which WP, along with a work plan and deadlines so that a scientific work agreement can be reached. A chairman of the working group might be appointed whose main role will be to coordinate discussions and chair the drafting and validation of the response document. He/She, should demonstrate experience, skills and competency in the field.

A 30-day period is granted for this secondary stage.

Important is to note that a request should be “feasible” in terms of:

- Resources;
- Partners availability;
- Skills;
- Deadlines.

Depending on the progress of the working group's discussions, the decision will be made as to whether the request should be fully or partially addressed (i.e., fulfilling only some aspects or parts of the request).

The MB will also be informed of the working group’s response at their following meeting.

Lastly, the response document will be presented to and validated by the GB, so that the final response can be sent to the applicant. GB members will have 5 days to contest the drafted response.

Co-leaders of Task 2.1 will then provide the applicant with the response document.

The whole process should take no more than 45 days and is resumed in the figure below.

Rapid Response Mechanism – Assessing an urgent request

If the request is approved and included in the partnership's framework, it will then be translated into a new project or activity or incorporated in the work of an ongoing project. Important is to note that there is a specific budget dedicated to urgent requests from the RRM. Furthermore, the new project / activity follows the same pattern as other projects and is therefore 45% funded by the EC and included in the next AWP.

3.2.2. Answering the request

A positive or negative response to the request is possible; in any case, it must be justified in the form of a "Response Document", to be sent to the applicant by the Task 2.1 co-leader within 45 days of the request's submission date. The "Response Document" format is described below, it includes the different stages of the request assessment to ensure a transparent approach. The characterization of uncertainties in the assessment or the response to this request is indeed important and should be included in the assessment.

It is important to remember that the purpose of the response document is to assist rapid and defensible decision-making about taking on board a new urgent request in PARC.

Response Document

Request: Restatement of the unsolicited request (title)

Sections of the scientific response document (15 pages maximum) should include:

1. **Summary:** request summary and background (including the policy context).
2. **Request eligibility under PARC:** assessment of the request's eligibility under PARC (comments from Task 2.1 and GB members).
3. **Inventory of available data/information:** depends on the request (Hazard, Exposure, Public Health, etc.).
4. **Analysis of available knowledge** (e.g.: usage of available data via modelling).
5. **Feedback from the working group meeting with the applicant:** conclusions drawn during the discussions and key points that lead to the decision.
6. **PARC's capacity to respond:** to identify how can PARC respond to the request, what kind of data/information will be generated, how the data/information should be used, under which WP the project will be developed, the estimated budget and the deadline for delivering results.
7. **Conclusion:** brief summary of the suggested response, approved by the GB
8. **References** (if any, for the available data section)

4. Example of the activation of the RRM

During a GB meeting on July 11th 2023, Sweden's GB PR, raised a new need that PARC should address. This need is related to the PFAS restriction proposal submitted to ECHA and the need for standardized analytical methods to screen PFAS in different matrices, enabling the application of the PFAS restriction in consumer articles. Given the potential of this request to activate and test PARC's conceptual RRM, the 'Request Template for urgent needs' was sent to her in order to get clarification on the request and its

potential use as a case study to activate the RRM. Below is the completed table outlining the details of this new request, Task 2.1 co-leaders received the filled-in template on October 2nd, 2023.

➤ Request formulation and Public Health concerns	
Problem formulation and policy context	<p>The PFAS restriction proposal initiated by five member states (Denmark, Germany, Sweden, Norway and the Netherlands) marks a new era in chemical regulation due to its scope. By aiming to restrict virtually all uses of more than 10 000 substances the proposal represents a major contribution to the zero-pollution ambition for a toxic free environment as expressed in the Green Deal. If successfully implemented, the restriction of PFAS can possibly lead the way to a more efficient group assessment of chemicals based on intrinsic hazard properties.</p> <p>A major challenge related to the implementation of the PFAS restriction, once it is in place, will be the difficulties for enforcement agencies to test consumer articles for compliance with the new legislation. Over the last decade, significant advances have been made in the analytical chemistry of PFAS to cover a broad spectrum of PFAS. At present there are many promising techniques that allow rapid screening and compound-specific validation of PFAS in different matrices. However, more work is needed to validate the methods and evaluate how they can be applied in a regulatory context. Some work to evaluate the regulatory needs for enforcement of PFAS in consumer articles is ongoing under PARC activity 6.4.3. It is envisioned that activity 6.4.3 will provide proof-of-concept methods for PFAS in major consumer article categories during Y3 and Y4 of PARC. Once the proof-of-concept methods have been developed additional work with testing of additional sample matrices, inter-laboratory validation and standardization needs to be performed. For this work we would like PARC to allocate resources from the extensive network of laboratories under WP4 and the capacity building resources under WP9.</p>
Public concern	Effective enforcement is necessary to ensure that emissions to the environment and exposure to EU citizens are lowered in line with the estimates of the proposal. Effective enforcement of the restriction is also paramount to ensure a level playing field for the producing industry within and outside of the EU and thus promote the desired substitution actions.
Research question	How should the quantity of PFAS in consumer articles be determined to assess compliance with the restriction proposal?
Objectives	The proposed action should help to deliver a suite of validated analytical methods for measurement of PFAS in consumer articles. The methods should ideally be incorporated into a technical guideline or ECHA forum compendium for enforcement.
Regulations	The proposed action will directly support the REACH restriction process of PFAS.
Timeframe to deliver the results	The methods for testing should ideally be in place 2025-2026 when the restriction of PFAS is in place.
Inclusion in the RRM	The Swedish chemicals agency has previously expressed the need for PARC to develop methods to support enforcement of chemicals legislation.
Link with the partnership	The Swedish chemicals agency is co-leader of PARC WP6.
Other initiatives	As mentioned above, work to address this need has been initiated under PARC 6.4.3.

Task 2.1 partners, together with GB members, had 10 working days to assess the eligibility of this request in PARC. The discussions took place in two stages: firstly, at the Task 2.1 meeting held in Copenhagen

on October 11, 2023, and then, at the GB co-chairs' online meeting on October 13. The request was also presented to the MB members at their meeting on October 2, and raised no objections.

Task 2.1 partners were in favour of considering the request eligible and moving on to the next stage which involves setting up a working group to study its feasibility. Indeed, the various eligibility criteria were discussed during the meeting and, this proposal met all of them. It's important to note that it was challenging to determine the urgency of this request and its inclusion in the RRM as this depends on the restriction and whether it will be adopted. Furthermore, the partners pointed out that industries could respond to this need, but that it would take a long time. Regulators must therefore ensure that regulations are enforced.

On another hand, the GB co-chairs were interested in this case study which they considered top on the agenda and gave the green light to proceed with the next step.

As a result of these positive viewpoints, a working group was set up to discuss the feasibility of this request.

A new project (P6.4.3.b_Y3_ENFORCE_Keml) has been proposed under WP 6, Activity 6.4.3, for PARC Year 3, with the aim of providing, by Year 4, proof-of-concept (POC) methods for PFAS in major consumer article categories, thus, addressing part of the new request. For this reason, experts and people that should be included in the working group were identified easily and a meeting with the requestor was held on Monday 13 of November, 2023. Following this meeting, a response document was drafted, adopted by the working group and approved by the GB co-chairs. The document was then sent to Sweden's GB PR on December 21, 2023. All the elements of the response document are provided in the Annex.

The GB members were always informed during their meetings on the progress of this PFAS request and, a presentation was made to the SF co-chairs during their meeting on January 30, 2024.

5. Discussion-Conclusion

The RRM is a key mechanism that enables PARC to fulfil its primary goal, the assessment of chemicals' impacts on human health and the environment and, to address them even in cases of urgent demands. It's worth noting that meeting the response deadlines and simultaneously securing engaged partners who are willing to provide person months (PMs) can be a demanding and challenging task. Nevertheless, PARC remains a valuable network and can provide a lot of opportunities. This RRM will be promoted via the website of PARC, its newsletter and PARCopedia; it will also be presented and clarified to the SF, the NHs and the GB members so they know how best to use it and activate it.

Annex: Response document of the PFAS urgent request

1. Request Summary

A new request was submitted under the Rapid Response Mechanism (RRM) on the 2nd of October 2023 by the Governing Board Principal Representative (GB PR) of Sweden. The request mainly addresses the enforcement of the PFAS restriction proposal⁷ submitted to the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) by 5 member states: Denmark, Germany, Sweden, Norway and the Netherlands. The proposal aims to restrict virtually all uses of more than 10 000 substances, presenting a major contribution to the zero-pollution ambition for a toxic free environment. In case this restriction is adopted, standardised analytical methods to detect PFAS in consumer articles will be needed.

At present there are many promising techniques that allow rapid screening and compound-specific validation of PFAS in different matrices. Nevertheless, more work is needed to validate the methods and evaluate their applicability in a regulatory context.

In fact, a new project (P6.4.3.b_Y3_ENFORCE_KemI) has been proposed under Workpackage (WP) 6, Activity 6.4.3 for PARC Year 3, with the aim of providing, by Year 4, proof-of-concept methods for PFAS in major consumer article categories. Once the proof-of-concept methods will be developed, the new request is to complete the work by testing additional sample matrices and performing inter-laboratory validation and standardization while collaborating with WP4 and WP9. The research question is as follow: How should the quantity of PFAS in consumer articles be determined to assess compliance with the restriction proposal?

2. Request Eligibility

At their meeting in Copenhagen on October 10, Task 2.1 partners discussed the eligibility of this request under PARC's framework. Then, on October 13, GB co-chairs also assessed the eligibility of this proposal during their online meeting.

The different eligibility criteria were assessed.

Task 2.1 partners were in favour of considering the request eligible and moving on to the next stage. Indeed, the request is in the scope of PARC, it is addressing a health and environmental concern, it is addressing a regulatory challenge and is not an emergency situation. Evaluating the urgency of this request and its inclusion in the RRM was challenging as this will depend on the restriction and whether it will be adopted. Furthermore, some partners pointed out that industries could respond to this need but it would take a lot of time and at this stage, it is good not to rely on private resources for this. Regulators must therefore ensure that regulations can be enforced. The remit of the Joint Research Centre (JRC) in this was also brought to discussion because part of their responsibilities is to develop methods for the enforcement of legislation, and there should be no duplication of effort. It was also stressed that duplication should be avoided with the European Commission's (EC) work on developing methods for the analysis of total PFAS in drinking water, given that a new limit value has been set, and also that methods might be developed for the enforcement of the PFAS restriction in fire-fighting foams⁸.

⁷ Link to the PFAS restriction proposal: <https://echa.europa.eu/-/echa-publishes-pfas-restriction-proposal>

⁸ Link to the restriction of PFAS in firefighting foams: [Registry of restriction intentions until outcome - ECHA \(europa.eu\)](#)

Similarly, the GB co-chairs took an interest in this case study which they considered top on the agenda and gave the green light to proceed with the next step.

3. Request Feasibility

3.1. Setting up a working group

In order to check the feasibility of this request, a call for experts was supposed to be made to set up a working group. As this is the first request, and since a new project proposed for Year 3 could already address a part of it, experts and people involved in the working group were identified easily. An invitation was sent to the requestor, the PFAS chemical leader, the WPs 4 & 6 co-leaders, the project managers of the new proposed project for year 3 (P6.4.3.b_Y3_ENFORCE_KemI) and, the according Project's Contact Point and reviewers from Task 2.1. A meeting was organised on Monday 13 of November. The aim of the meeting was to verify the feasibility of the new request within PARC, to discuss on its integration in the proposed new project for year 3 and, reflect on the various items of the response document. Not all parts of the response document were applicable for discussion (inventory of available data – analysis of available knowledge), so the sections here differed from those planned and reported in the RRM deliverable.

The table below lists the attendees of the working group's meeting.

Name	Role in PARC
Pascal Sanders	PARC Coordinator
Christophe Rousselle	PARC Deputy Coordinator
Basile Cazalis De Fondouce	Coordination Team member
Maria Tannous	Task 2.1 member
Uhl Maria	WP2 co-leader
Nicole Bandow	WP4 co-leader
Rima Souki	WP4 SPF representative
Lina Wendt - Rasch	WP6 co-leader
Marion Sanders	WP6 representative involved in RIVM PFAS restriction
Ing-Marie Olsson Ressonner	GB PR for Sweden
Robin Vestergren	A 6.4.3 co-leader, PM of new proposed project
Lisa Emily Melymuk	A 6.4.3 co-leader, PM of new proposed project
Safia Korati	T2.1 member
Ignacio De La Flore Terejo	ECHA PFAS restriction team
Laure-Anne Carton de Tournai	T2.1 Reviewer (ECHA)

3.2. Request assessment

An initial discussion focused on the P6.4.3.b_Y3_ENFORCE_KemI project, which will provide, by Year 4 of PARC, a proof-of-concept (POC) methodology for testing compliance with the proposed PFAS restriction in selected groups of consumer articles (Report 1 in Month 54). The project managers were confident that the POC methodology is achievable, it will be based on a tiered approach building on all that has been done, with a decision tree, involving several individual analytical methods. In fact, the project team includes PFAS analysts capable of designing a tiered approach. Important is to note that one of the team partners (ÖRU/ Örebro University, Sweden) is a consultant in the EC's work on the total PFAS

analytical methodology for analysing total PFAS in drinking water. Thus, the project can focus on methods that will be complimentary to those developed for drinking water and fire-fighting foams.

This project proposal was reviewed by two reviewers from Task 2.1 who approved it without conditions. They also found it very interesting without doubting on its regulatory relevance.

In a two years' timeframe, when the POC will be ready, the methods, especially those that are robust and, (ideally) rapid and cheap, will need to be tested further. Using PARC's network of laboratories within Europe will be needed for the validation of these methods and for building the expertise, to make sure they can be applied routinely by a large spectrum of laboratories across EU and are broadly accepted by agencies and industries. In this way, laboratories will be able to share their experience and evaluate the methods. Preliminary research for project P6.4.3.b_Y3 showed that some of the currently used analytical techniques for PFAS, including total fluorine approaches, can be standardized and that ISO standards already exist for some of them. A 6.4.3 will identify what can be achieved in terms of standardization for the various individual methods for which different levels of standardization will be possible.

It was agreed that, as the proof of concept will be ready in Year 4, this will leave some time to come up with a new project proposal for the standardisation of the methods. In fact, the submitted project 6.4.3b will partially answer to the request; then, at the end of the project, there will be a milestone to decide on the next step and develop a follow up project. The five Member States of the PFAS restriction proposal are involved in PARC, ensuring that support will be there. The new project will be a transversal WP project, starting in year 5, gathering WPs 4 - 6 and 9. In this direction, new resources will be needed for this new project, these resources cannot be determined at the moment because this will depend on recommendations from P6.4.3b. In the meantime, it is critical to identify the right contacts and identify partners with potential interest or even external interested parties working on similar topic in order to revisit the resources. This, will also depend on the aspects of instrumentation needed and the laboratories that can be involved. If consultation of the National Hubs (NHs) is needed (through questionnaires for example), collaboration with WP3 is possible. Furthermore, exchanging with the scientific and analytical community in PARC, regarding the established tiered approach, can be done through PARC's [website](#), [PARCopedia](#) or the [SYNnet](#). It was also stated that the level of PFAS in the types of materials to be detected or monitored must be defined and a target for control and for monitoring purposes should be ensured. All of this will be shaped once the project of Y3 is launched.

To sum up, the project 6.4.3b have the following objectives: i) to provide a good state-of-art view (overview of the different kinds of methods and different levels of the tier approach, long-term view of the methodologies....) based on the overview already established by the submitters of the restriction dossier as part of this dossier, ii) to design a proposal to support the implementation of the PFAS restriction through different processes (establishment of a network of laboratories under WP9, establishment of standards if needed, training of people on the establishment...) and, iii) think about what kind of validation process should be applied according the purpose of the method. In fact, the next steps were difficult to judge from current knowledge at the meeting of the working group. Considering the widespread usage of PFAS in different industrial processes and consumer applications, the project will focus on the major categories of consumer products described in the restriction proposal.

It was brought to the table that the main focus of WP4 is to carry out monitoring studies in order to provide monitoring data and not to validate methods. However, collaboration WP4 can be foreseen, in particular with task 4.3 for the development of methods. In addition, as WP9 maps-out training needs, it might be relevant to include, for the next round, the need of a training for these methods because WP4 focuses mainly on non-targeted screening methods, effect-based methods and new sampling methods for human biomonitoring.

Finally, all work will be carried out in parallel with other initiatives at EU level aiming to enforce the restriction on PFAS, this should be taken into account through close exchanges with the Governing Board, European agencies and the EC.

4. Conclusion

Having validated and standardized methods for the enforcement of the PFAS restriction is important. The response to this first request addressed via the RRM, will be a two-step process. In the first stage, the project P6.4.3.b_Y3_ENFORCE_KemI will ensure a POC methods for PFAS in selected consumer articles based on a tier approach. This first step will be completed by Year 4, in order to proceed with the design of a new joint project for Year 5. This new project will aim at creating a network of laboratories that will be involved in testing and gaining expertise in these methods so that they can, in the longer term, continue this type of monitoring. This second project will certainly require additional resources than the ones from the project starting in Year 3. These resources will depend on the methods and cannot be communicated at present. Once the project is launched in Year 3, it will be possible to have a clearer vision of how the project will be extended and what resources need to be added and mobilised.